

STUDIES ON METAL FERROCYANIDES. PART I. VOLUMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM BY FERROCYANIDE

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Precipitations with ferrocyanide solutions of varying concentrations have been carried out with different concentrations of the metal salt solutions. From a study of the various complex metal ferrocyanides formed, the possibility of quantitative determination of metals by ferrocyanide precipitation is suggested.

The present determination of Cd is based on the quantitative precipitation of the complexes $K_2CdFe(CN)_6$ and $3K_2CdFe(CN)_6 \cdot Cd_2Fe(CN)_6$, with dilute and moderately strong solutions of potassium ferrocyanide. The accuracy of the determination appears to lie within the limits of phase changes of the different complexes.

Formation of complexes of cadmium and ferrocyanide has been reported by earlier workers (Williams, "Cyanogen Compounds", 1948, p 181; Tananaev and Kozlov, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1951, 6, 149; Belcher, Nuttan and Stephen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3444). According to them the composition of the different complexes formed, depends on the concentration of the cadmium and ferrocyanide solutions. Review of literature, however, shows that the p_H of the medium as also the presence of non-interfering electrolytes stabilises many of the complexes. During studies in these laboratories on different metal ferrocyanides, it was observed that the addition of cadmium chloride solution of varying concentrations to an excess of freshly prepared potassium ferrocyanide solution containing a non-interfering electrolyte like potassium chloride led to the precipitation of $K_2CdFe(CN)_6$ and $3K_2CdFe(CN)_6 \cdot Cd_2Fe(CN)_6$, the former with dilute solutions and the latter with moderately strong solutions of ferrocyanide. The present authors have worked out the amount of cadmium that can be determined by the present method.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. stock solution of $CdCl_2$ was prepared by dissolving a known quantity of B. D. H., A. R. quality $CdCl_2$ in water. The weight of Cd in this solution was determined by the iodine method (Thompson and Mellor, "A Treatise on Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1938, pp. 180, 376). Pure (Merck sample) potassium ferrocyanide solutions of different concentrations, varying from 1 to 4% were prepared and exact concentrations determined by titrations with standard ceric sulphate (Willard and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3260). A standard solution of ceric sulphate was prepared by the method of Meyer and Aufrecht (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 140).

A known quantity of the cadmium solution was pipetted into a 250 c.c. flask, and a known excess of potassium ferrocyanide solution added. About 50 c.c. of a 2% solution of KCl was added, the volume made up to 250 c.c. and kept aside overnight with frequent shaking. The precipitate was filtered through Whatman No 50. First few c.c. of the filtrate containing excess of ferrocyanide was thrown off after rinsing the flask

and 50 c.c. of the filtrate was pipetted out, 20 c.c. of 4-5*N*-H₂SO₄ and a drop of phenanthroline ferrous complex as indicator were added to it and titrated against a standard ceric sulphate solution. A preliminary titration of a known quantity of ferrocyanide was carried out against the standard ceric sulphate solution.

Different concentrations of the ferrocyanide, varying from 4 to 1% solution, were tried and the accuracy of the method for different concentrations of cadmium worked out. For the titration relationship the precipitate appears to have the composition CdK₂Fe(CN)₆ and 3CdK₂Fe(CN)₆. Cd₂Fe(CN)₆ or Cd₂K₄[Fe(CN)₆]₃, according as concentrations of 1% and 2-4% of ferrocyanide solutions used. A typical set of results is shown in Table I.

TABLE I

CdCl ₂ soln.	Conc. of ferrocyanide.			Wt. of Cd by ferrocyanide.	Wt. of Cd by I ₂ method.	Diff.
5 c.c.	50 c.c. of 1% soln			0.02701 g.		0.00004
	25	2	"	0.02699	0.02705 g.	0.00006
	25	4	"	0.02699		0.00006
10	50	1	"	0.05395		
	50	2	"	0.05395	0.05411	0.00016
	25	4	"	0.05395		0.00016
15	75	1	"	0.08042		
	50	2	"	0.08091	0.08116	0.00025
	25	4	"	0.07993		0.00123
20	75	1	"	0.10900		
	75	2	"	0.10900	0.10810	0.00090
	25	4	"	0.10690		0.00120
25	100	1	"	0.13700		
	75	2	"	0.13700	0.13530	0.00170
	50	4	"	0.13480		0.00250
30	100	1	"	0.15990		
	50	4	"	0.15990	0.16233	0.00243

The results show the variation of the complex with the variation in concentration of the alkali ferrocyanide. With the ferrocyanide solution of 4 to 2% strength, the formation of the complex Cd₂K₄[Fe(CN)₆]₃, afforded quantitative determination of Cd, whereas solutions of 1% strength precipitated the complex CdK₂Fe(CN)₆ only. It is thus inferred that the concentration of the alkali ferrocyanide plays an important part in the formation of Cd-ferrocyanide complexes.

The precipitate and the solution have to be kept standing for a definite time, say 12 hours, and it is essential to add some non-interfering electrolytes, such as KCl, to allow the precipitated complex to settle and also to increase the size of the particles (to prevent the passing down of the fine precipitate through a filter). Whatman No. 50 filter was found most suitable for the purpose.

The formation of the complexes mentioned above, under the conditions specified, have been supported by the conclusions of earlier workers (*loc. cit.*).

Apart from the accuracy of this new volumetric procedure for the determination of Cd, its essential advantage lies in the use of ceric sulphate as a standard titrant, for the indirect titration of ferrocyanide.

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